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High-temperature thermal and mechanical properties of aerogel/fibrous zirconia ceramic composites

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OUTLINE

1. Introduction

- **Porous ceramics:**
fuel-cell electrodes, ceramic filters, catalyst supports and thermal barriers.

C. Hong, Scripta Mat. 60 (2009), 563

L Hu, Ceram.Inter. 36 (2010),1697

- Recently, porous **zirconia** ceramics for the potential applications in thermal insulations have drawn more attention, due to its low thermal conductivity, corrosion resistance and high-temperature resistance.

1. Introduction

- **Fibrous porous ceramics:**
 - bird's nest-like structure;
 - low density, low thermal conductivity, reasonable high mechanical strength,
 - good for using as thermal insulations.

- **Aerogels:** ideal thermal insulation materials, consisting of a nanostructured network with high porosity (up to 90%), having extraordinary properties:
 - ultralarge specific surface area (500-1200 m²/g),
 - ultralow density (0.003-0.35 g/cm³)
 - ultralow thermal conductivity (0.012-0.1 W/(m·K)).

Silica aerogel

1. Introduction

- The above studies were mainly focused on the room-temperature properties, high-temperature properties of the aerogel/fibrous ceramic composites have not been studied systematically, which are important for high-temperature insulators.
- Objective: In order to further decrease the thermal conductivity as well as to improve thermal insulation performance, **alumina aerogel** was impregnated into the porous **fibrous zirconia ceramics**. The present work aimed at investigating the microstructure, thermal and mechanical properties at high temperatures of **the aerogel/fibrous zirconia ceramic composites**.

2. Experimental

◆ Preparation procedures

Precursor: Aluminum chloride hexahydrate ($\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Aldrich, 99%), a mixture of distilled water and ethanol were used as solvent, and propylene oxide (PO: Aldrich, 99%) was used to initiate the condensation reaction.

The solution was introduced into the porous ceramics by vacuum-infiltration. After aging, the alumina aerogel/fibrous ceramic composites were obtained **by a supercritical drying process** ($T_c=243^\circ\text{C}$, $P_c=6.3\text{ MPa}$).

2. Experimental

After the aerogel impregnation, the specimen's density slightly increased from 0.75 to 0.78 g/cm³, due to the ultralow density of the aerogel.

◆ Characterization and Tests

- (1) **Microstructure**: a ZEISS scanning electron microscopy (SEM)
- (2) λ_{RT} : a EKO analyzer (sample size: 150 × 150 × 20 mm)
- (3) **High temperature insulation performance**: The back temperature test, hot surface T=1400°C, for 30min. The sample's cold surface T was recorded (sample size:150 × 150 × 20 mm).

3.1 High-temperature dimensional stability

- Dimensional stability: an important factor to determine a material's working temperature for practical applications.
- After heating at 1400°C for 30 min, the aerogel/ceramic composite had a very small linear shrinkage of 2%, which was much less than that of a monolithic alumina aerogel.

The comparison of BET values for two aerogels

unit: m²/g

Heating T	SiO ₂ aerogel	Al ₂ O ₃ aerogel
original	598	520
1000°C,30min	556	341
1100°C,30min	9.4	222
1200°C,30min	/	126

3. Results & discussion

(a) Fibrous ceramics

(b) the aerogel/ceramic composites

(c) aerogel

- (a) The alumina aerogel occupied most of the pores between the fibers, resulting a significant decrease in pore size.
- (b) The aerogels were nanostructure materials with nanosized particles and nanosized pores.

3.1 High-temperature dimensional stability

SEM images of the composites after heating at 1400°C for 30min

3.1 High-temperature dimensional stability

The microstructural evolution with temperature for the composites revealed:

- (1) The aerogel occupied the pores of the fibrous ceramics, resulting in a significant decrease in pore size. The aerogel's particle size and morphology changed with increasing temperature.
- (2) The growth tendency of the aerogel particles in the composites was much less than that of the monolithic aerogels. This should be due to the better thermal insulation of the fibrous porous ceramic framework compared to air, which suppressed heat transfer to the aerogels in the composites.

Such phenomenon indicates that the aerogels in the composites could maintain structural stability at higher temperatures than the monolithic aerogels.

3.1 High-temperature dimensional stability

(3) after heating at 1400°C , the aerogels in the composites changed from filling the fibers' pores to mainly attached on the fibers' surface. Thus, the aerogels' volume shrinkage did not cause the 3-D fibrous ceramic framework to shrink, which were consistent with the composite's small shrinkage after heating at 1400°C .

Therefore, the good dimensional and structural stability suggest that the obtained composite could be a candidate for thermal insulation working at high temperatures up to 1400°C .

3.2 High-temperature insulating properties

sample	λ_{RT} (W/m·K)
Fibrous ceramics	0.055 ($\rho=0.75$)
the aerogels/ceramic composites	0.046 ($\rho=0.78$)

It was attributed to the effective suppression of the gaseous and radioactive heat transfer by impregnating the porous ceramics with aerogel.

3.2 High-temperature insulating properties

Back-temperature tests for the ceramic sample and the aerogel/ceramic composite

when the hot-face temperature was 1400°C for 30 min, the samples' cold-face temperature decreased from 960°C to 880°C after impregnation with aerogel.

3.3 High-temperature mechanical properties

sample	Compressive strength at RT after 1400°C for 30min (MPa)	Compressive strength at RT after 1400°C for 30min (MPa)
Fibrous ceramics	0.9	0.6
the aerogels/ceramic composites	1.1	0.3

- The RT compressive strength did not decrease, which is agreement with the results in literature.
- However, the degradation of σ_c for the composites after heating at 1400°C probably resulted from the microstructural damage of aerogels at high temperatures.

4. Conclusions

Impregnating the fibrous zirconia porous ceramics with alumina aerogel is an effective way to improve thermal properties at temperatures up to 1400°C.

However, the degradation of mechanical properties at 1400°C should be considered for thermal insulation applications with load-bearing requirements at high temperatures.

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